

Eventually, the affected leaf blade withered and dropped off.

The causal organism was isolated on potato dextrose agar. A pathogenicity test was performed by placing a drop of mycelial fragment prepared from 7-d-old culture at the collar region during

the late booting stage. Affected collar regions were collected and placed in sterile petri dishes lined with moist filter paper.

The fungus produced numerous pycnidia on the affected tissue. Pycnidia were dark, separated, immersed in host

tissue, and ostiolate. Conidia were hyaline, oblong, rounded at both ends, 14-15 × 4 µm.

The causal fungus was identified as *Ascochyta oryzae* Catt. This is the first record of its occurrence in Manipur. ■

Effect of some leguminous crops on number and viability of *Sclerotium oryzae* sclerotia

S. Hussain, Pulses Programme, National Agricultural Research Centre, Islamabad 45500; and A. Ghaffar, Botany Department University of Karachi, Karachi, Pakistan

In the crop rotation pattern of Pakistan, rice usually follows wheat. Leguminous crops which have the ability to restore soil fertility by fixing N from atmosphere also are planted as dry season crops.

We studied the effect on rice of growing a leguminous crop in soil infested with sclerotia of *S. oryzae* (the cause of stem rot in rice). Wheat was planted as a control. The experiment was laid out in a complete block design with four replications.

Berseem (*Trifolium alexandrinum*) gram (*Cicer arietinum*), lentil (*Lens*

Table 1. Effect of leguminous crops on number and viability of *Sclerotium oryzae* sclerotia. ^a Sheikhpura, Pakistan.

Crop rotation ^b	1986 wet season		1986-87 dry season		1987 wet season	
	Population	Viability (%)	Population	Viability (%)	Population	Viability (%)
R-W-R	9 a	63 a	8 a	70 a	8 a	87 a
R-L-R	8 a	60 a	10 a	78 a	7 a	74 a
R-G-R	9 a	52 a	10 a	64 a	13 a	83 a
R-B-R	14 b	73 a	8 a	41 b	6 a	89 a

^a In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at P < 0.05 by Duncan's Multiple Range Test. ^b R = rice, W = wheat, L = lentil, G = gram, B = berseem.

culinaris), and wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) were planted in Nov and harvested in Apr. Rice (*Oryza sativa*) was transplanted in Jun and harvested in Oct. Recommended NPK was applied. Sclerotia were separated from soil by sieving and flotation technique after harvest of each crop. Their viability was tested on water agar supplemented with streptomycin sulfate and penicillin at 3,000 ppm each.

Population and viability were reduced up to 43% after berseem; there were no significant reductions in sclerotia after

Table 2. Effect of a leguminous crop on rice yield. Sheikhpura, Pakistan.

Crop rotation	Rice yield ^a (t/ha)	Yield Increase (%)
Wheat - rice	5.1 c	-
Lentil - rice	5.2 bc	3
Gram - rice	6.0 b	17
Berseem - rice	6.9 a	35

^a Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at P < 0.05 by Duncan's Multiple Range Test.

rice (Table 1). Rice yields increased significantly when berseem was used in the rotation (Table 2). ■

Etiology of grain discoloration in upland rice in West Sumatra

J. Castano, K. Klap, and Z. Zaini, Sukarami Research Institute for Food Crops, P.O. Box 34, Padang 25001, West Sumatra, Indonesia

Rice grain discoloration is becoming a serious problem in tropical rice production areas, particularly in upland rice. In Indonesia, it is common to find the disease in upland rice grown in acid soils, such as the red-yellow Podzolic soils of West Sumatra.

We collected seeds of susceptible upland rice cultivar Tondano and panicles of local upland rice cultivars Arias and Simariti showing different levels of disease severity. The seeds were seeded after the agar plate test and incubated in a

Microorganisms associated with grain discoloration levels (1, 10, 30, 60, 100%) in upland rice. West Sumatra, Indonesia.

Microorganism	Microorganisms (%) at indicated level of grain discoloration				
	1%	10%	30%	60%	100%
<i>Helminthosporium oryzae</i>	14 ^a	17	22	41	40
<i>Trichoconis padwickii</i>	50	30	14	5	7
<i>Phoma</i> sp.	12	34	24	30	2
<i>Nigrospora</i> sp.	12	8	13	8	7
<i>Curvularia</i> sp.	9	7	15	7	8
<i>Torula</i> sp.	3	1	1	3	9
<i>Mycovellosiella oryzae</i>	1	4	0	3	0
<i>Cercospora janseana</i>	2	2	0	1	0
<i>Phyllosticta</i> sp.	0	2	1	2	0
<i>Chaetomium</i> sp.	0	0	0	5	0
<i>Gerlachia oryzae</i>	1	0	2	0	0
<i>Phomopsis</i> sp.	0	2	0	1	0
<i>Cercospora oryzae</i>	0	0	1	2	0
<i>Penicillium</i> sp.	2	0	0	0	1
<i>Gonatobotrys</i> sp.	1	0	0	0	0
<i>Macrophoma</i> sp.	0	1	0	0	0
<i>Memnoniella</i> sp.	0	1	0	0	0
<i>Helicoceras oryzae</i>	0	0	1	0	0
<i>Fusarium</i> sp.	0	0	0	0	1
<i>Diplodia oryzae</i>	0	0	0	0	1

^a Data from 100 seeds.

chamber at 20-25 °C and a 12-h day/night NUV light cycle. Pathogenicity tests were carried out.

Twenty fungi genera were identified (see table). *H. oryzae* was the most common fungus isolated. Pathogenicity tests reproduced typical grain discoloration symptoms. ■

Integrated pest management — insects

Leaffolder (LF) outbreak in Punjab, Pakistan

M. Salim, A. Rehman, and M. Ramzan, Rice Programme, National Agricultural Research Centre, Islamabad, Pakistan

The rice LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Gn), long considered a minor pest of rice in Pakistan, has attained the status of a major pest in the last few years, and has caused considerable losses to the rice crop. During the 1989-90 crop season, the pest multiplied enormously, with severe incidence observed during Aug-Sep.

We conducted a survey of LF incidence on 2,941 ricefields at 73 locations in eight rice-producing districts of the Punjab.

The crop was severely damaged in Sheikhupura, Sialkot, and Gujranwala Districts (see figure). Infestation was 51% at Dirdhe Dogran in Sheikhupura. In Sialkot, Jassarwala showed 25% infestation. In Faisalabad, Okara, Kasur, Lahore, and Gujrat Districts, infestations were less than 10%.

About 80% of the rice area was planted to Basmati 385, a fine, aromatic,

Leaffolder incidence in the Punjab, 1989.

Leaffolder infestation as affected by different factors in ricefields. Punjab, Pakistan, 1989-90.

	Infestation (%)							
	Variety				Cultural		Environmental	
	Basmati 370	Basmati 385	Kashmira	Palman	Early crop	Late crop	Shady areas	Nonshaded areas
	13.7	15.6	5.3	70.3	10.3	35.0	40.7	13.7
	10.9	15.5	4.7	45.9	7.5	23.5	55.9	13.9
	15.1	16.2	8.5	85.0	7.2	27.2	72.3	15.3
	15.7	20.5	7.2	40.5	6.3	39.1	42.0	17.2
	8.5	13.4	6.3	57.9	13.8	40.2	45.9	10.3
	10.7	10.6	3.4	55.9	10.9	24.3	65.1	20.5
	17.2	19.7	6.3	55.0	12.1	20.5	70.5	17.2
	8.7	20.3	3.7	47.5	9.0	29.5	69.2	21.0
	11.5	17.5	5.6	69.7	13.4	40.0	50.1	15.3
	14.5	16.7	5.8	45.2	8.5	22.2	49.5	10.2
Mean	12.7	16.6	5.7	57.3	9.9	30.2	56.1	15.5

and high-yielding variety. Average damage to this crop was 16.6%; damage on Basmati 370, Kashmira, and Palman was 12.7, 5.7, and 57.3%, respectively

(see table). Infestation in the late crop was higher than in the early crop. Infestation in shady areas was much higher than in nonshaded areas. ■

Sugarcane pest found in Sulawesi ricefields

D. Baco, S. Sama, and A. Hasanuddin, Maros Research Institute for Food Crops, P.O. Box 173, Ujung Pandang, South Sulawesi, Indonesia

The sugarcane mite *Aceria* (= *Eriophyes*) *saccharini* (Wang) was

first reported in Java by van Hall in 1923. It was discovered on rice at Maros Experimental Farm in 1988. Damage symptoms had been noticed for several years before identification.

In 1989, the mite damaged more than 775 ha of rice in South and Central Sulawesi. Rice plants show brownish yellowing leaves about 3-4 wk after

transplanting. In heavier infestations, plants exhibit stunting. Up to 1,000 mites/leaf can occur. Infestations are heavier in the dry season.

Indonesian rice varieties Cisadane, Pelita I-1, and Cisanggurang are more resistant to the mite than are IR26, IR42, IR48, and IR64. ■